

A Study on Viscosity of Magnesium Soaps in Water and Methanol

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The viscosity of magnesium soaps in water and methanol has been measured over a temperature range 35-50°C. The critical micelle concentrations are found to be independent of temperature but decrease with increasing chain length of the soap. The equations of Vand and Moulik are applicable only above the CMC of soaps. The parameters of equations may be used to calculate the viscosity of soap solutions in concentration range in which the equations hold good. The temperature effect on viscous flow follows Arrhenius equation. The effect of soap concentration on fluidity of soap solutions has been discussed in the light of Eyring's equation and the activation parameters of viscous flow ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* have been calculated.

RECENT studies^{1,2} of the conductance of magnesium soaps in water and alcohols have indicated the presence of micelles. In order to obtain a better and general understanding the viscosity of these soaps have been determined in water and methanol. The viscosity data have been interpreted in terms of various viscosity equations with a view to find out the nature of micelles formed in these solvents under different conditions and confirm the results obtained from conductivity measurements^{1,2}.

Experimental

The chemicals were purified and the soaps were prepared by the method described in the previous communication¹. An Ostwald viscometer was used to determine the viscosity of soap solution in a thermostatically controlled ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) bath. The densities were measured with an accuracy of ± 0.0001 g. with a dilatometer.

FIG. 1 PLOTS OF VISCOSITY VS CONCENTRATION OF MAGNESIUM VALERATE SOLUTIONS IN WATER

FIG. 2 PLOT OF $1/c$ VS $1/Loa \eta/\eta_0$ OF MAGNESIUM CAPROATE IN METHANOL AT 35-50°C.

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Results and Discussion

The viscosity, η of the systems increases with increasing soap concentration. The plots (Fig. 1) of viscosity vs. concentration of the soap are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a concentration 0.01, 0.01 and 0.005M indicating the formation of micelle³ for valerate, caproate and caprylate respectively at different temperatures. It appears that at equal concentrations longer molecules impart greater viscosity. But the extrapolated values of viscosity for zero soap concentration in water and methanol are in agreement with the corresponding experimental values at various temperatures and are independent of chain length of the soaps ; the soap molecules do not aggregate appreciably below CMC.

The viscosity of magnesium soap solutions has been satisfactorily represented by the following^{4,5} equations :

$$\text{Vand : } \frac{1}{C} = (0.921/\bar{V})^{-1} \cdot 1/\log (\eta/\eta_0) + Q\bar{V} \quad (i)$$

Fig. 3 PLOT OF $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ VS C^2 OF MAGNESIUM VALERATE IN METHANOL AT 35-50°C

Where Q and \bar{V} are the interaction coefficient and molar volume of the solute in litre mole⁻¹, respectively, and C is the concentration of the solute in moles litre⁻¹

$$\text{Moulik : } (\eta/\eta_0)^2 = M + K^1 C^2 \quad (ii)$$

Where M and K^1 are constants.

The plots (Figs. 2 and 3) of $\frac{1}{C}$ vs. $1/\log (\eta/\eta_0)$ for equation (i) and $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs. C^2 for equation (ii) are found to be linear in a limited range of concentration (Tables 1 and 2). Both the tables reveal that the equations are valid in the concentration range above CMC. The values of molar volume, \bar{V} , have been calculated from the slopes ($=\bar{V}/0.921$) of the plots of $1/C$ vs. $1/\log (\eta/\eta_0)$ and the results are given in the Tables 1 and 2.

It has been observed that the value of \bar{V} increases with an increase in temperature in methanol. The values of \bar{V} of magnesium caprylate in water show similar behaviour as in methanol but values of other soaps remain constant with increase in temperature. It should be pointed out that the molar volumes of caproate and caprylate in methanol are higher than those in water.

The interaction coefficient, Q , calculated from the intercept ($=Q\bar{V}$), increases with increasing temperature (Tables 1 and 2). It may be pointed out that these values decrease in water and increase in methanol with increasing chain length of the soap.

TABLE 1—VISCOSITY PARAMETERS FOR MAGNESIUM SOAP SOLUTIONS IN WATER AT 35-50°C.

Temperature in °C	Tested Conc. limit. (moles/litre)	Valid Zones (moles/litre)	\bar{V}	Q	M	K^1
<i>Magnesium valerate</i>						
35	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	0.97	-24.81	1.038	42
40	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	1.02	-21.66	1.055	43
45	0.003—0.05	0.02—0.05	1.04	-18.34	1.056	36
50	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	0.92	+32.57	1.058	40
<i>Magnesium caproate</i>						
35	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	0.94	-27.07	1.055	35
40	0.003—0.05	0.02—0.05	1.07	-23.27	1.064	36
45	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	1.07	-19.14	1.097	27
50	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	1.07	-15.44	1.116	24
<i>Magnesium caprylate</i>						
35	0.003—0.02	0.005—0.01	4.22	-51.40	1.014	260
40	0.003—0.02	0.005—0.01	4.84	-40.32	1.058	320
45	0.003—0.02	0.005—0.01	5.07	-31.58	1.062	400
50	0.003—0.02	0.005—0.01	5.30	-25.49	1.086	340

TABLE 2—VISCOSITY PARAMETERS FOR MAGNESIUM SOAP SOLUTIONS IN METHANOL AT 35-50°C

Temperature in °C	Tested Conc. limit (moles/litre)	Valid Zones (moles/litre)	\bar{V}	Q	M	K^1
<i>Magnesium valerate</i>						
35	0.003—0.02	0.01—0.05	0.61	-25.66	1.024	43
40	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	0.064	-20.02	1.032	45
45	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	1.38	-3.98	1.044	50
50	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	1.53	-1.96	1.053	48
<i>Magnesium caproate</i>						
35	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	1.90	-23.71	1.074	30
40	0.003—0.05	0.01—0.05	1.93	-17.61	1.082	70
45	0.003—0.05	0.02—0.05	1.96	-8.18	1.138	68
50	0.003—0.05	0.02—0.05	2.00	-6.40	1.146	66
<i>Magnesium caprylate</i>						
35	0.003—0.05	0.005—0.01	4.97	-7.64	1.066	500
40	0.003—0.02	0.005—0.01	5.34	-3.56	1.071	500
45	0.003—0.02	0.005—0.02	11.42	-0.65	1.143	350
50	0.003—0.02	0.005—0.02	14.55	-0.54	1.152	320

In order to compare the applicability of both the equations the values of K^1 and M have been calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the plots of $(\eta/\eta_0)^2$ vs. C^2 and the results are given in Tables 1 and 2. It has been observed that the values of M of caproate and caprylate are higher in methanol than in water and increase with increasing temperature. The constant K^1 does not show any definite trend in variation with temperature. It is of interest to note that the values of K^1 of caprylate are exceptionally higher than other systems.

It may be mentioned that Vand's equation contains a defined parameter, \bar{V} , the interaction coefficient, Q is only approximately obtained⁶. It appears that most probably Q is a specific property of a solute and it is not the general property⁷. The parameters M and K^1 of Moulik's equation are not yet defined.

Several empirical and theoretically derived relationships connecting viscosity and temperature have been proposed⁸⁻¹⁰ from time to time. The equation of Arrhenius

$$\frac{1}{\eta} = A \exp(E\phi/RT) \quad (\text{iii})$$

has been found to hold good for the soap solutions. The term $E\phi$ is defined as the energy required to transfer 1 g. mole of the solute from one position of equilibrium to another and may be identified as the activation energy of the viscous flow. A is a constant. According to Ward, this energy is associated with the configurational changes produced by shearing and depends upon interatomic and intermolecular forces etc.

The plots of $\log \eta$ vs. $1/T$ are straight lines in various solvents. The activation energy of the viscous flow, $E\phi (= \Delta H^*$ in Table 3) has been calculated from

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR FLUIDITY OF MAGNESIUM VALERATE IN WATER AND METHANOL.

Conc. of soap in moles litre ⁻¹	Water			Methanol		
	ΔH^* K. cal. mole ⁻¹	ΔS^* Cal. deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	ΔG^* K. cal. mole ⁻¹	ΔH^* K. cal. mole ⁻¹	ΔS^* Cal. deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	ΔG^* K. cal. mole ⁻¹
0.000	3.22	3.53	2.136	2.63	0.51	2.468
0.003	3.340	3.91	2.137	2.65	0.85	2.389
0.005	3.400	4.09	2.139	2.67	0.91	2.390
0.010	3.46	4.26	2.140	2.70	0.98	2.394
0.020	3.57	4.59	2.152	2.74	1.11	2.399
0.030	3.63	4.75	2.166	2.79	1.24	2.405
0.040	3.69	4.93	2.170	2.83	1.37	2.412
0.050	3.75	5.08	2.179	2.88	1.49	2.419

the slopes of the linear plots. The interpretation of viscous flow according to the theory of absolute reaction rates has also been presented by Eyring and coworkers^{1,2}. The temperature dependence of reciprocal viscosity (fluidity), $1/\eta$ has been evaluated in terms of the Eyring's equation,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\eta} &= \left(\frac{V}{hN} \right) \exp(-\Delta G^*/RT) \\ &= \left(\frac{V}{hN} \right) \exp(-\Delta H^*/RT) \exp. \\ &\quad (\Delta S^*/R) \end{aligned}$$

The Arrhenius activation energy, E_0 has been taken as equal to ΔH^* , the Eyring energy of activation and the Arrhenius coefficient, A has been equated with $\left(\frac{V}{hN} \right) \exp(\Delta S^*/R)$ to obtain ΔS^* , the entropy of activation. h and N are Planck's constant and Avogadro number respectively, V is the molar volume of the solvent, R is the gas constant in cal.deg⁻¹ mole⁻¹, T is the absolute temperature and η is the viscosity in poise. Free energy of activation, ΔG^* is then calculated at 35°C from Gibb's equation.

The activation energy of viscous flow, ΔH^* and entropy, ΔS^* (Table 3) both show a little change below CMC but above CMC there is an appreciable linear increase. ΔH^* measures energy barrier to fluid motion and the increase in ΔH^* with concentration indicates less fluidity and thus confirms structured solvent and the micellar aggregation. Since the ΔG^* controls the rate of flow, which is governed by the slowest step in the fluid process, the data suggest that below CMC there is essentially no new process than the flow of pure water. It is considered that non linearity of free energy of activation for fluidity with the concentration of an added solute becomes indicative of the formation of solute-solvent aggregate^{1,3}, as the principal kinetic entity. Here it is observed that plots of $\Delta G^* - C$ are

linear above CMC. Therefore, solvent-solute aggregation is not occurring but the aggregated soap molecules (micelles) remain in an overall ordered surroundings. The slopes of the linear plots of ΔG^* vs. C are 1.0, 0.8 and 2.4 K cal. mole⁻² litre in water and 0.6, 0.4 and 1.3 K. cal. mole⁻² litre in methanol for valerate, caproate and caprylate, respectively.

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